

Effect of Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate on 7S Fraction of Soybean

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The major storage proteins of soybean are 7S (β -conglycinin) and 11S (glycinin) globulins and the understanding of the individual protein fraction is essential for their better utilisation. We have been studying the proteins of oilseed storage proteins with the objectives of characterising them¹. A method has been developed to isolate the 7S protein of soybean seeds in homogeneous form and it gave four nonidentical subunits in sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis². Since the 7S fraction is oligomeric, the effect of denaturants on purified protein fraction is of utmost importance to know the aggregation and dissociation or unfolding of protein. Thus in continuation of our earlier work^{1,3} on the effect of denaturants on storage proteins, we report herein the effect of sodium

dodecyl sulphate (SDS) on gel-filtration pattern, ultraviolet difference spectra and reduced viscosity of soybean 7S protein.

Results and Discussion

The reduced viscosity gradually increased with increasing concentration of SDS and attained a value of 8.34 ml/g at 10.41 mM SDS concentration (Table 1). Addition of SDS beyond this concentration precipitated the protein, therefore, viscosity data could not be recorded at higher SDS concentrations. Rapeseed protein showed a maximum value of 10.4 ml/g at 17.34 mM SDS while for mustard protein, a steady value of 11.5 ml/g was reached at 17.34 mM SDS concentration⁴. A

NOTES

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SDS CONCENTRATIONS ON REDUCED VISCOSITY OF 7S FRACTIONS OF SOYBEAN

Temp. = 25°, Protein concn. = 1.5 g/dl

SDS concn. mM	Reduced viscosity ml g ⁻¹
0.00	5.23
1.74	6.18
3.47	6.75
6.94	7.13
10.41	8.34

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SDS ON ABSORBANCE OF 7S FRACTION* (PROTEIN SOLUTIONS HAVING AN ABSORBANCE OF 0.75 AT 280 nm WERE USED WHEN SDS WAS NOT PRESENT)

SDS concn. mM	ΔA_{280} nm	ΔA_{295} gm
1.73	-0.029 7	-0.050 4
3.47	-0.005 0	-0.014 8
6.94	-0.032 5	0.020 5
10.41	0.047 0	0.021 8
13.87	0.037 4	-0.077 0
17.34	-0.000 7	-0.291 7
20.81	-0.170 2	-1.421 8

*Protein solutions having absorbance of 0.75 at 280 nm were used when SDS was not present.

reduced viscosity of 23 ml/g for various proteins in the completely random coil conformation has been reported⁵. In the present results, the highest reduced viscosity value was not a steady value, suggesting that even at 10.41 mM SDS concentration, the protein did not attain random coil conformation.

ΔA_{280} and ΔA_{295} nm were recorded for 7S fraction in the presence of various concentrations of SDS (Table 2). Negative difference spectra were observed in the presence of 1.74 and 3.47 mM SDS, whereas positive difference spectra were observed when SDS concentration was raised to 10.41 mM SDS. Again the difference spectra became negative when the protein was exposed to 17.34 and 20.81 mM SDS concentration.

The increase in absorption at 6.94 and 10.41 mM SDS concentration indicate exposure of tyrosine

and tryptophan residues, possibly due to dissociation of 7S fraction into subunits. The decrease in absorption at higher SDS concentration (17.34 and 20.81 mM) could be due to the aggregation of dissociated subunits.

Elution profile of gel filtration pattern of 7S protein in the presence of various concentration of SDS (Fig. 1) indicates that absorbance at 280 nm decreased by higher SDS concentration. Since SDS does not absorb at 280 nm, the decreased absorbance may be due to altered protein conformation. V_e/V_0 (elution volume/void volume) of 7S protein without SDS was found out to be 1.47. In the presence of 1.74 mM SDS, the major peak remained in its position while a minor peak at V_e/V_0 value of 2.2

Fig. 1. Elution profile of gel filtration pattern of 7S fraction of soy protein (100 mg) in the presence of various concentrations of SDS.

was observed (Fig. 1). At 3.47 mM SDS, two main peaks were observed with V_e/V_0 value of 1.47 and 1.93. The minor peak at V_e/V_0 of 1.93 could be due to the dissociation of protein molecule into its subunits.

V_e/V_0 value of 1.93 shifted to 2.0 as concentration of SDS was increased to 6.94 mM SDS, while the major peak at V_e/V_0 of 1.47 remained unaffected. At 10.41 mM SDS, minor peaks at V_e/V_0 of 0.93 and 2.07 were observed in addition to major peak at 1.47. Peak having V_e/V_0 value of 0.93 suggests aggregation of the subunits of 7S fraction. At higher SDS concentration of 13.87 mM, three distinct peaks could be seen having V_e/V_0 values of 0.93, 1.53 and 2.13. Again at 17.34 mM SDS the major peak remained at V_e/V_0 of 1.47 and another minor peak at V_e/V_0 of 0.93 was observed. The disappearance of peak at V_e/V_0 of 2.13 suggests that majority of the dissociated subunits of 7S protein have been reaggregated. Thus the present results suggest that dissociation of protein into subunits occurred upto 6.94 mM SDS concentration. The aggregation of these subunits was again observed at 17.34 mM SDS concentration.

Experimental

The purified 7S fraction was obtained by the method reported earlier^{2,3}. For this purpose, crude extract of 7S fraction from defatted soybean meal was obtained by the reported method⁶ in Tris buffer of pH 6.6. Then 55–100% ammonium sulphate precipitated 7S fraction was dispersed in standard buffer (32.5 mM K_2HPO_4 , 2.6 mM KH_2PO_4 , 0.4 M NaCl, pH 7.6, 10 mM 2-mercapthanol) and purified by gel filtration technique. This purified 7S fraction was found to be homogeneous by polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and was used for denaturation studies. The effect of SDS was studied using the following techniques.

Gel filtration: Sepharose-6B (Agarose gel) which had been equilibrated with 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.6) containing 0.4 M NaCl was packed into a column (2 × 50 cm). The protein (100 mg) solution was loaded to the column. When the experi-

ment was performed in the presence of SDS, the column was pre-equilibrated and eluted with buffer containing the appropriate concentration of SDS. Fractions of 5 ml each was collected and absorbance was measured at 280 nm. The void volume (V_0) of column was found by loading dextran blue.

Viscosity: The viscosity measurements were carried out in a Ubbelohde viscometer having a flow time of 288s with the phosphate buffer. The flow time of 7S fraction was measured in the absence and presence of different concentrations of SDS.

Uv difference spectra: In an attempt to know whether aromatic side-chain residues of protein acquire an altered environment as a result of denaturation, the difference spectra was measured. Moreover, difference spectra at 280 nm originated mainly from exposure of tyrosine residues while at 295 nm due to tryptophan residues. Therefore, change in absorbance (ΔA_{280} and ΔA_{295}) produced by the addition of different amount of SDS to 7S fraction against identical protein concentration was recorded on a Beckman DU-7 spectrophotometer.

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